

Improving the collection and summarization of audit evidence in audit organizations

O'layev Sukhrob Temur o'g'li
Assistant of Tashkent State
University of Economics
s.ovlayev@tsue.uz

Yo'lchiyev Oybek Ulug'bek o'g'li
Assistant of Tashkent State
University of Economics
o.yulchiev@tsue.uz

Abstract. In this article, in the effective organization of the audit of audit organizations, there are methods such as collecting the issues of audit evidence in a suitable and specific situation and the principles used in determining the audit evidence, as well as methods of performing analysis based on evidence.

Keywords. Audit evidence, audit working papers, audit report, audit report, audit report, audit review, sufficiency of evidence, relevance of evidence, analysis of evidence

Introduction. When conducting an audit of financial statements of economic entities, it collects the necessary evidence to determine whether the financial statements comply with regulatory legal documents or the existence of deviations from the scope of the law.

Audit evidence available in the course of auditing financial statements may take various forms. In organizations, during the audit process, auditors gather assets, liabilities or other necessary evidence, information obtained as a result of third-party confirmation that transactions actually took place, etc., are of great importance.

Literature review. The method of collecting, compiling, storing, formalizing and presenting evidence on the results of the auditor's investigation is defined in the international audit standard No. 500 "Auditor's evidence". According to this standard, "Audit evidence is the information used by the auditor in reaching the conclusions that form the basis for the auditor's opinion".

The scientific literature on auditing has studied and applied the opinions presented by several economists about audit evidence and audit report. According to economist SMBichkova, audit evidence is considered as a "fact" and a "process". Evidence means that it can serve to confirm or deny the existence of another fact or process,

information about a specific fact that allows forming a conclusion about the reliability of financial statements.¹

In addition to this, another approach, according to V.B.Ivashkevich, "audit evidence is a documented source of information obtained as a result of the audit of accounting"²Also, foreign economist J. Robertson defines evidence as follows: "audit evidence is information that determines the auditor's actions in obtaining information, that is, it affects the opinion of auditors and determines their decisions."³

Another economist A.K.Ibragimov said that Audit evidence is the data obtained by the auditor during the audit and the result of the analysis of this data, based on which an audit conclusion is drawn.

Professor R.D.Rajaboyev (R.D.Rajaboyev, 2010) stated that the audit evidence is the information obtained from the client-enterprise and third parties and the results of their analysis, which allows to draw up an audit opinion on the reliability of the financial report. .

Russian scientist Ya.V Sokolov (Ya.V.Sokolov, 2012) revealed the importance of audit evidence in his research work. Also, Professor H.N.Musaev (H.N.Musaev, 2002) categorized the audit evidence according to such criteria as: order of obtaining, method of obtaining, justification and place of origin.

Professor Z.T.Mamatov (Z.T.Mamatov, 2004) also grouped the audit evidence according to three criteria (internal, external, mixed) and disclosed the methodological aspects of its application in the audit of financial statements. Also, the issues of applying statistical methods to the collection of audit evidence have been studied.

Auditing is important according to the timely audit report and final conclusion. For this purpose, it is appropriate to distinguish these two terms, i.e. audit report and audit conclusion. In this regard, in the opinion of Professor I. Quziev, "The audit report is the audit evidence collected during the audit, detailed information about deviations in accounting, irregularities in the financial statements, as well as the results of the audit it is defined as a report consisting of other information received."⁴

Mainly foreign economists conducted scientific research on the process of gathering evidence and its generalization of the auditing methodology. E.A.Arens, Dj.K. Lobbek, A.D.Sheremet and V.P.Suyts can be included in their list. In particular,

¹Бйчкова С.М. Доказательств в аудите / С.М. Бйчкова. - М.: Finance and statistics, 1999. - 176 p.

²Ивашкевич В.Б. Завершающая стадиум аудитор'с ческер / В.Б. Ивашкевич // Аудиторские ведомости – 2007. – No. 11. - S. 3–7.

³Robertson Dj. Audit / Dj. Robertson. - М.: KPMG, Auditorskaya firma "Kontakt", 1993. - 496 p.

⁴N. Koziyev. Issues of drawing up audit reports and conclusions on the results of audit inspections. Scientific electronic magazine "Economy and innovative technologies". No. 4, July-August, 2015.

according to E.A.Arens and Dj.Lobbek (E.A.Arens and Dj.Lobbek, 2012), "Understanding the relationship between international and national standards and audit evidence and audit procedures is important in auditing."⁵

Economists of our republic have studied these issues in the textbooks, monographs and training manuals, as well as in the published scientific articles and theses, only the aspects of the organization of audit activities and gathering of evidence. For example, in the works of R.D.Dusmuratov, N.F.Karimov, Z.T.Mamatov, M.M.Tolakhujaeva, I.N.Quziev, B.Q.Hamdammov and I.I.Meliev, the problems of gathering evidence and summarizing this process were studied in the audit.

The above-mentioned studies of several scientists on audit and audit evidence, opinions and definitions related to these concepts, in general, have both theoretical and practical aspects.

It was clearly demonstrated that the foundation consists of the necessary knowledge.

Research methodology. Systematic analysis, logic, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis, and grouping methods were used in the research work. According to the processed and recorded data, scientific conclusions are given.

Analysis and results

During the collection of audit evidence, it is decided to use a representative sample for the audit of the auditors. Audit evidence should be sufficient to achieve audit objectives determined by auditors based on audit practice. In the process of gathering evidence, questionnaire tests can be used, during which the strengths and weaknesses of the internal control and accounting of the organization being studied are determined. In the process of analyzing the operations of the organization under audit, the auditor works based on the forms of financial statements. When conducting an audit of financial statements, the auditor must have sufficient knowledge of the client's business to understand the events, transactions, and practices that may materially affect the financial statements, the audit, or the auditor's opinion. Based on this, the financial statements and several operations of the relevant JSC enterprises were studied. The analysis of profitability indicators based on the financial report of "FERGONA GRAIN PRODUCTS" JSC is explained below.

Table 1

Required indicators from the 2023 annual financial report of "FERGONA GRAIN PRODUCTS" JSC.⁶

⁵Arens EA, Lobbeck Dj.K. Audit: per. English / Gl. editor's series prof. Ya. V. Sokolov - M.: "Finance and Statistics", 2012. - 560 p.:il.

⁶Prepared by the author.

No	Indicators	Last ear	Reporting ear
1.	Gross profit from the sale of products (goods and services).	31,641,539	6,879,144
2.	Net income from the sale of products (goods and services).	296,622,007	205,019,882
3.	Income from financial activities	1,072,420	160,454
4.	Expenses on financial activities	1,872,612	2,007,698
5.	Net profit for the reporting period	15,725,112	
6.	Assets	294,367,423	228,860,060
7.	Passives	294,367,423	228,860,060
8.	Main activity benefit	19,645,205	
9.	Obligations	8,716,477	
10.	Private capital	220,143,583	
11.	Average annual value of assets	261,613,741.5	

Based on the financial report of "FERGONA GRAIN PRODUCTS" JJ, profitability indicators are found as follows.

Profit on sales= Gross profit on sales / Net revenue on sales

Return on assets = net profit / average annual value of assets

Operating profit = operating profit / net sales

Return on equity = net profit / equity

Table 2

**Indicators analyzed based on the annual financial report of 2023 at
"FERGONA GRAIN PRODUCTS" JSC⁷**

No	Indicators	%
1.	Profitability of sales	0.033
2.	Return on assets	0.060
3.	Profitability of operating activities	0.066
4.	Return on equity	0.071

Based on the 2023 annual financial report of FERGONA GRAIN PRODUCTS JSC, the indicators analyzed are return on sales at 0.033%, return on assets at 0.060%, return on operating activity at 0.066%, and return on equity at 0.071%. is showing. Sufficient audit evidence allows the auditor to draw a clear and reasonable conclusion about the financial results of the organization being audited. Sufficiency

⁷ Prepared by the author.

of the evidence is a process that requires sufficient qualification from the auditor and is formed during professional judgment in this regard. Here are some factors to consider in this case:

- The more qualitative the audit evidence, the less quantitative it is collected. In this case, it should be noted that the quality of audit evidence is inversely related to its quantity.

- Another important rule in gathering evidence in an audit is the level of materiality. That is, depending on how important or not important the object being investigated is, it is required to collect more or less information. Obviously, it is possible that insufficient evidence will be gathered when concluding the important objects, which will cause the quality of the work to be violated and the wrong conclusion to be made. It is from this point of view that evidence should be collected in sufficient quantity for important objects in terms of quality and quantity.

The subject of the audit includes the collection and study of information about economic facts, which is to a greater extent the legality, validity, and determination of appropriateness, allows obtaining a sufficient amount of qualitative and important evidence to determine the reliability and validity of the indicators of the accounting (financial) report of the organization.

Before and during the audit, all performed procedures and received information (audit evidence), recorded conclusions are reflected in the auditor's working documents.

Conclusion. A number of factors are important for auditing organizations in our country to continue their activities effectively and transparently. Currently, in the investigations carried out by the organizations, several illegal situations such as failure to provide necessary documents, making changes to financial statements or making mistakes in the account book are noted. Naturally, such shortcomings have a negative impact on the auditor's work. In particular, the evidence collected in this regard is considered invalid and affects the quality of the conclusions.

In our opinion, primary documents, accounting registers, results of financial analysis, inventory materials, accounting reports should be accurate and reliable as sources of audit evidence. If the auditor uses different forms of presentation of evidence from different sources, then the audit risk is reduced. The most reliable evidence is obtained from independent sources (from third parties), independent analysis and written form. In this case, it is appropriate to present the audit organization with an officially certified presentation letter justifying the fact that all information serving to form a fair and reliable conclusion about the financial report has been provided on the date of the audit report.

In our opinion, the importance of this presentation letter is that, firstly, the responsibility of the client's management is ensured for serious violations in the

financial statements due to the fact that some documents that affect the reliability of the financial statements were not studied in the post-audit inspections.

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